

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: "Asymmetry in Civic Information: An Experiment on Tax Participation among Informal Firms in Togo"

Evaluator 1 Evaluator 2 David Reinstein

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ABSTRACT

We organized two evaluations of the paper: "Asymmetry in Civic Information: An Experiment on Tax Participation among Informal Firms in Togo" [1]. Both evaluations are generally positive (journal tier ratings approaching 'top field journal'), and also offer critiques and suggestions for improvement. Both evaluators provide suggestions for the interpretation of the results and their implications, request more detail, especially about the treatment delivery, and express concerns with sample size and power. Evaluator 1 sees the lack of administrative data as a key limitation, and suggests ways the authors might do more to address this. They ask for further consideration of the MLEs' experience with tax officials, and specific identification robustness checks involving matching. Evaluator 2 is concerned about causal identification, suggesting that using same enumerators at baseline and endline could violate an exclusion restriction. They also express doubts about whether the survey measures reflect beliefs about "accountability", among other concerns. To read these evaluations, please see the links below.

Evaluations

1. [Evaluator 1](#)
2. [Evaluator 2](#)

Overall ratings

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment (See footnote¹)

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5): On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' should this be published in?² *Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.*

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Evaluator 1	85	4
Evaluator 2	75	3.5

See "[Metrics](#)" below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators' ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).³

See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.

Evaluation summaries

Anonymous evaluator 1

This paper uses a randomized experiment among informal firms in Togo to explore how civic tax information affects compliance and economic activity. While overall tax participation falls, the intervention leads to more accurate self-reporting among larger firms and economic expansion among smaller ones. The findings challenge standard views on tax education and offer novel insights into state–firm dynamics in low-capacity settings. With some clarifications, the paper makes a valuable contribution to the literature.

Anonymous evaluator 2

This paper reports an RCT of a taxpayer education campaign in Togo, showing increased tax knowledge, a shift in the distribution of tax payments, and higher reported revenues. The [evaluation] finds the study valuable in its focus on small firms and the large tax knowledge effects. It offers suggestions concerning measurement bias due to enumerator involvement in the intervention, accountability measures, and interpretation of payment effects.

Metrics

Ratings

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.

	Evaluator 1 Anonymous			Eval. 2 Anon.
Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments	Rating (0-100)
Overall assessment ⁴	85	(75, 95)		75
Claims, strength, characterization of evidence ⁵	85	(75, 95)		
Advancing knowledge and practice ⁶	85	(75, 95)	Z	

Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ⁸	85	(75, 95)	9	
Logic & communication ¹⁰	90	(80, 100)		
Open, collaborative, replicable ¹¹	85	(75, 95)		
Real-world relevance 12 , 13	90	(80, 100)		
Relevance to global priorities ¹⁴ , ¹⁵	90	(80, 100)		

Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator 1			Evaluator 2	
	Anonymous			Anonymous	
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Comments	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI
On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	4	(3.7, 4.7)		3.5	N/A

What 'quality journal' do you expect this work will be published in?	4	(3.3, 4.7)	16	N/A	N/A
See here for more details on these tiers.	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 				

Claim identification and assessment (summary)

For the full discussions, see the corresponding sections in each linked evaluation.

	Main research claim ¹⁷	Belief in claim ¹⁸	Suggested robustness checks ¹⁹	Important 'implication', policy, credibility ²⁰
Evaluator 1 Anonymous	Thus, even though tax participation has decreased, tax revenue likely increased in the aggregate. Tax information shapes tax behaviour in complex ways: providing firms with knowledge about their tax obligations reduces overall tax participation but results in heterogeneous effects, increasing compliance among larger firms and decreasing it among smaller firms.	The claim is thought-provoking but the described mechanisms seems plausible. Potential robustness, and future research can help disentangling other potential explanations behind the result.	A follow-up study conducted in collaboration with the revenue agency and linking participants to their anonymized tax records would be compelling.	As highlighted in my evaluation, the findings carry important implications for state capacity and legitimacy. Civic education initiatives should be tailored to the specific socio-institutional context, as simply increasing information may not uniformly enhance compliance.

Evaluation manager's discussion

Author's engagement: The authors have been helpful and encouraging, sharing their latest work and discussing the paper's status. They have indicated they intend to respond to these evaluations at some point further along in the journal publication process. If so, we will post this response here.

I am planning to wait for this response before discussing the package further in this section.

(From David Reinstein)

References

1. Blimpo, M. P., & Castañeda Dower, P. (2025). Asymmetry in Civic Information: An Experiment on Tax Participation among Informal Firms in Togo. Working paper. Earlier version: https://novafrica.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/2021.12.10_Moussa-Blimpo.pdf

Footnotes

1. We asked them to rank this paper "heuristically" as a percentile "relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years." We requested they "consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice. ↵

2. See ranking tiers discussed [here](#). ↵

3. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. ↵

4.

Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.

↵

5. "Do the authors do a good job of (i) stating their main questions and claims, (ii) providing strong evidence and powerful approaches to inform these, and (iii) correctly characterizing the nature of their evidence?"

This was on the newer form only ↵

6.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

⇐

7. The project offers relevant insights into tax compliance in informal sectors, with clear implications for state-building and development policy in low-capacity settings. ⇐

8. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? ⇐

9. The methods are clearly explained and appropriate, with a well-justified RCT design. Assumptions are reasonable, and the authors acknowledge key limitations. ⇐

10. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? ⇐

11.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

⇐

12.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

⇐

13.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

”Are the paper’s chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?”

“Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do

they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↵](#)

14. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? [↵](#)

15.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↵](#)

16. Journal of Development Economics can be a reasonable prediction [↵](#)

17.

The evaluator was given the following instructions:

Identify the most important and impactful factual claim this research makes – e.g., a binary claim or a point estimate or prediction.

Please state the authors' claim precisely and quantitatively. Identify the source of the claim (i.e., cite the paper), and briefly mention the evidence underlying this. We encourage you to explain why you believe this claim is important, either here, or in the text of your report. [↵](#)

18. Evaluators were asked: To what extent do you *believe* the claim you stated above? Feel free to express this either a. in terms of the probability of the claim being true, b. as a credible interval for the parameter being estimated, or c. however you feel comfortable. [↵](#)

19.

We asked:

[Optional] What additional information, evidence, replication, or robustness check would make you substantially more (or less) confident in this claim?

Feel free to refer to the main body of your evaluation here; you don't need to repeat yourself. Please specify how you would perform this robustness check (etc.) as precisely as you are willing. E.g., if you suggest a particular estimation command in a statistical package, this could be very helpful for future robustness replication work. [↵](#)

20.

We asked:

[Optional] Identify the important **implication** of the above claim for funding and policy choices? To what extent do you **believe** this implication? How should it inform policy choices?

Note: this 'implication' could be suggested by the evaluation manager in some cases. As an example of an 'implication' ... in a global health context, the 'main claim' might suggest that a vitamin supplement intervention, if scaled up, would save lives at a \$XXXXX per life saved.

We did not ask this in the 'applied stream' as it is most likely redundant.

⇐

References

1. Blimpo, Moussa P., and Paul Castañeda Dower. 2025. *Asymmetry in Civic Information: An Experiment on Tax Participation among Informal Firms in Togo*. ⇐